

INSTRUMENTS DEVELOPMENT FOR THE ABILITY TO SOLVING MATHEMATICS STORY QUESTIONS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This research aims to develop an instrument for elementary school students to solve mathematics story problems. Students' ability to solve math story problems is often a challenge, and previous research shows that these difficulties can be overcome through appropriate instruments. In this context, the ADDIE Model is used as a framework for developing educational instruments. Considering the low ranking of Indonesian students' mathematics abilities in international assessments, this research is necessary. The question instrument was created using the Rasch Model to obtain fit question items and analyze the Winsteps software output results. This measurement aims to provide information that can be used in developing better item instruments related to the ability to solve math story problems. This research shows the importance of developing appropriate and valid instruments to measure students' abilities in solving mathematics story problems. Using the ADDIE Model, instrument development can be carried out in a structured, practical and focused manner. The results of this research can improve the mathematical problem-solving abilities of elementary school students in Indonesia.

Keywords: Development of Educational Instruments, Mathematical Problem Solving Ability, Mathematical Story Question Instruments, Elementary School.

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a knowledge that everyone needs in everyday life. Mathematics is widely used in everyday life. Good skills in using mathematics are necessary for solving problems in everyday life. Mathematics learning is carried out from elementary to tertiary level, so Indonesian students will likely have good skills. The better Indonesian students' skills in Mathematics, the better the quality of education in Indonesia will be. Evaluation is needed to determine the quality of education in Indonesia. For this purpose, Indonesian students have taken part in several international scale assessments. Several international scale assessments include PISA (The Program International Student Assessment) and TIMSS (The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study).

Indonesian students' mathematics abilities can be proven to be at the bottom of the PISA (The Program for International Student Assessment) activities for children aged 15 years in Mathematics, Science and Literacy. Since Indonesia participated in the first PISA from 2000 until 2018, Indonesian students have been in the lowest position among participating countries (Budi, 2018; OECD, 2015). Indonesia's ranking experienced a significant increase in score in 2015 by 11 points, but the ranking is still below OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation Development) countries. The results of the latest release in 2018, Indonesia's ranking fell again. Indonesia is ranked 7th from the bottom (Permana, 2019; Program, Assessment,

2018). Since Indonesia participated in the first PISA from 2000 until 2018, Indonesian students were in the lowest position of the participating countries (Budi, 2018; OECD, 2015b). Indonesia's ranking experienced a significant increase in score in 2015 by 11 points, but the ranking is still below OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation Development) countries. The results of the latest release in 2018, Indonesia's ranking fell again. Indonesia is ranked seventh from the bottom (Permana, 2019; Program, Assessment, 2018).

The PISA ranking of Indonesian students in Mathematics in 2000 had an average score of 367 points, which was ranked 39th, then in 2003, it had an average score of 360 points, which was ranked 38th, then in 2006, it had an average score of 391 points, which was ranked 50th. In 2009, it had an average score of 371 points, which was ranked 61st; in 2012, it had an average score of 375 points, which was ranked 64th. Then, in 2015, it had an average score of 386 points, which was ranked 62nd, and finally, in 2018, it had an average of 379 scores with a ranking of 67 (Permana, 2019; Program, Assessment, 2018). Based on the PISA report, Indonesian students' abilities in Mathematics are in the low category and need to receive optimal attention.

Large-scale assessments have been enhanced to measure student ability in the reading, mathematics, and science content domains. The Trend in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) is a large-scale international and prestigious assessment in Mathematics and Science. TIMSS was first held in 1995 and is carried out every 4 years from 1999, 2003, 2007, and so on by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA).

The main goal of TIMSS is to act as an educational policy maker and educator through reliable and timely data. As a reliable basis for improving their educational performance. TIMSS cognitive domain (Prastyo, 2020): knowing, applying and reasoning. TIMSS ability levels, namely: level 1 advanced ability, level 2 high-level ability, level 3 intermediate-level ability, and level 4 low-level ability. TIMSS Indonesia results from 2003 to 2015 including in 2003, it was ranked 35th with an average score of 411 points, then in 2007 it was ranked 36th with an average score of 397 points, then in 2011 it was ranked 38th with an average score was 386 points and in 2015 it was ranked 44th with a total average score of 397 points (Hadi & Novaliyosi, 2019; Nizam, 2016).

The TIMSS score categories are a score of 400 in the low category, a score of 475 in the medium category, a score of 550 in the high category, and a score of 625 in the very high category (Hadi & Novaliyosi, 2019; Nizam, 2016). Based on the information above, Indonesia's position from 2003 to 2015 was in the low category.

The factors that cause students to experience learning difficulties consist of internal factors and external factors. Internal factors include students' attitudes towards learning, students' learning motivation, intellectual abilities and students' physical health. Meanwhile, external factors include more variety in teachers' teaching methods, inadequate use of media, school facilities and infrastructure, and a less supportive family environment (Unaenah et al., 2022; Cahyono, 2019).

Students' mathematical problem-solving abilities can be interpreted as students' ability to understand problems, plan problem-solving strategies, implement the chosen solution strategy, and re-examine the solution to the problem so that the solution can then be taken systematically and inseparably from the correct representation of the problem (Polya, Batubara, 2017 ; Siagan et al., 2019). Story problems are an essential part of the mathematics curriculum in elementary schools (Kurshumlia and Vula, 2019). Story questions have an essential role that is usually used to determine students' problem-solving abilities. Story problems are questions considered to have a higher level of difficulty than mathematics questions that display mathematical models directly. In story problems, students are expected to be able to find problems that must be solved in the problem (Dwidarti et al., 2019). The problem that students often need helping in learning mathematics is solving word problems.

Other facts also show that students' mathematical problem-solving abilities still need to improve. This is proven by research conducted by Sol et al., 2020; Pertiwi et al., 2021; Simamora et al., 2019; Surya et al., 2017; Meryansumayeka et al., 2021; Hasbi et al., 2019; Wasiah et al., 2020; Utami et al., 2018; students experience students' inability to solve mathematical problems.

Mathematical ability is a person's ability to memorize, understand, explain and apply mathematical concepts to solve problems in everyday life. One form of application for solving mathematical problems in everyday life is using story problems (Utami and Endaryanto, 2018). The ability to complete math word problems is an essential skill in students' mathematical development at the elementary school level based on research conducted by Patel et al., 2021; Cobbe et al., 2021; Tambunan, 2019; Kenedi et al., 2019; Math word problems allow students to apply mathematical concepts in real-life situations, helping them develop a deeper understanding of mathematics and problem-solving skills.

We can see students' difficulties in solving math problems in the form of story problems from their ability to read, understand, process, transport, solve process skills and write answers (Surya, 2018) based on Newman's theory of five important activities in learning to bring out students' abilities in solving story problems. Includes the following five stages: (1) reading, (2) understanding, (3) transformation, (4) process skills, and (5) writing answers/encoding (Sesanti and Bere 2020). Problems experienced by elementary school students who experience errors in solving story problems based on the Polya procedure include the following four stages: (1) understanding the problem, (2) making a plan, (3) implementing the plan, (4) checking again (Utami et al., 2019; Yuwono et al., 2018; Vilianti et al., 2018). Solving math word problems is more challenging than solving multiple-choice questions or short descriptions. Story problems require students to understand the problem in the story, determine strategies, carry out strategies, and conclude answers (Octavia, 2017). They need a good understanding of mathematical concepts, analyzing problems, and applying their knowledge. As students move to higher levels, the difficulty level of math word problems tends to increase. An instrument is needed to evaluate students' abilities in solving mathematical story problems.

Measuring the ability to solve math story problems can be challenging to do. The instruments used to measure this ability must consider the diversity of types of story questions, difficulty level, and cognitive abilities being tested. Developing appropriate and valid instruments is essential to understand student abilities accurately. The ADDIE model is an instructional design development model with a learner-centered learning approach rather than a traditional teacher-centered approach so that effective learning can occur (Harmelin, 2022). Each learning component is regulated by learning outcomes, which have been determined after thoroughly analyzing student needs. These phases sometimes overlap and can be interrelated, but they provide dynamic and flexible guidelines for developing effective and efficient teaching.

The ADDIE model is a framework for the development of educational instruments. A theoretical study of this model will help researchers understand the steps to develop educational instruments, including analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. The advantages of the ADDIE model for developing instruments to solve story problems include being structured, practical and focused (Harmelin, 2022). Compared to using the previous model, it requires a relatively long time because the procedure is relatively complex and requires quite significant financial resources, as in the Borg and Gill development model (Maydiantoro, 2021). Applying the ADDIE Model to develop an instrument for solving math story problems for fourth-grade elementary school students has never been done before. The development of story problem-solving instruments using the ADDIE Model has been carried out by several researchers, with research subjects being middle-class and upper-class students, as evidenced by research conducted by (Rochsun & Agustin, 2020; Prabowo et al., 2020; Riyati & Suparman, 2019; Azzatia, 2019).

Based on learning difficulties, especially in the ability to solve math story problems experienced by fourth-grade elementary school students, the researchers wanted to develop an instrument for the ability to solve math story problems for fourth-grade elementary school students in Depok City. Questions were discussed in the Number Domain in the Odd Semester of the 2023-2024 Academic Year. Question items in the Number Domain include numbers and their place values, the value of the rupiah currency, the most significant common factor and the smallest common multiple. Student ability measurements are carried out after the Mid-Odd Semester learning activities. This measurement can be used as a reference for developing the items related to the ability to solve story problems (word problems).

Statement of the Problem

The author focuses on two instrument development processes, including measuring elementary school student's ability to solve mathematics story problems. The steps to achieve this goal will include needs analysis, instrument design, development, implementation, and evaluation. Then, the research will explore the characteristics of the developed test items, with particular emphasis on each question item's difficulty level. Thus, this research will provide in-depth insight into developing an effective evaluation instrument and understanding the critical aspects that must be considered in developing mathematics story questions for elementary school students.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this research includes several main concepts relevant to the development of an evaluation instrument for students' abilities in solving student-centered mathematics story problems by applying the ADDIE Model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation), which will be used as a framework for the development of evaluation instruments. The ADDIE model emphasizes the importance of analyzing students' needs, designing appropriate instruments, developing them, implementing them, and evaluating their effectiveness.

Understanding the characteristics of mathematics story problems and the difficulty level of the questions will be an essential basis for developing the instrument. This concept includes an understanding of reading, understanding, transformation, process skills, and writing answers in solving story problems. Thus, this theoretical framework will help develop appropriate and effective evaluation instruments, considering an understanding of mathematical problem-solving, student-centered learning models, and the characteristics of mathematical story questions and their difficulty level.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research and development methods. The method in this research is a combination of instrument development and research and development models. This research aims to evaluate elementary school students' understanding and skills in solving mathematical story problems, focusing on measuring their achievement in the mathematical concepts contained in the word problems. This research assesses the potential positive impact of using the developed instrument on improving elementary school students' learning and understanding in solving mathematics story problems, focusing on the practical application of research results in an educational context.

The research and development model is used to produce specific products and test the product's effectiveness (Donovan, 2013; Zulyadaini, 2017). In this research, the product is an instrument for solving story problems in elementary school mathematics. The development research model used is the ADDIE model. The research and development model of the ADDIE Model (Branch, 2009; Branch, 2013; Sharifah & Faaizah, 2015; Muruganatham, 2015; Hess & Greer, 2016; Zulyadaini, 2017) includes: 1) Analyze, 2) Design, 3) Development, 4) Implementation, and 5) Evaluation.

The target population in this study was limited to grade IV elementary school students in Depok City. Meanwhile, the affordable population is represented by class IV students at SDN with An accreditation and the Merdeka Curriculum. Phase I of the trial is a small-scale sample, followed by data collection, and phase II is the actual sample. The samples used were five elementary schools in Depok City, with a sample size of 500 respondents.

The instrument was tested for validity by 4 experts to see the validity of the content of the development of the school mathematics story question instrument. The analysis obtained valid evidence, showing that the Aiken' V content validity score was 0.81. This proves that the

mathematical content related to the development of the Story Question Instrument is by the measurement objectives or measurement accuracy (Heale & Twycross, 2015). The test-retest reliability of the mathematics story problem instrument was ensured. The scores obtained from the two responses were subjected to statistical analysis involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation at a significance level of 0.05. This instrument produces a reliability coefficient of 0.918, which is considered high enough for this research.

RESULTS

This research is intended to seek information and data that can be used to empirically describe the quality of test instruments based on elements of validity and reliability, which are processed with the help of the Rasch model and Winsteps software. Following are the results of phase 1 of the trial

Table 1: Data on the distribution of misfit or unfit questions using the Rasch model for the first test

ENTRY NUMBER	TOTAL SCORE	COUNT	MEASURE	MODEL		INFIT		OUTFIT		PT-MEASURE		EXACT MATCH		ITEM
				S.E.	MNSQ	ZSTD	MNSQ	ZSTD	CORR.	EXP.	OBS%	EXP%		
17	43	200	1.28	.18	1.06	.7	1.19	1.4	A	.13	.24	78.0	78.6	S17
15	31	200	1.70	.20	1.03	.3	1.16	.9	B	.14	.22	85.0	84.5	S15
14	93	200	.02	.15	1.11	2.5	1.16	2.9	C	.13	.30	60.5	63.0	S14
10	53	200	.98	.17	1.07	.9	1.15	1.4	D	.14	.26	73.0	73.7	S10
16	98	200	-.09	.15	1.11	2.4	1.13	2.5	E	.15	.31	54.5	62.9	S16
8	129	200	-.79	.16	1.10	1.6	1.11	1.6	F	.16	.30	65.5	67.8	S8
22	85	200	.20	.15	1.08	1.8	1.11	1.8	G	.18	.30	56.0	63.6	S22
9	44	200	1.24	.18	1.05	.6	1.10	.8	H	.16	.25	78.5	78.1	S9
21	70	200	.55	.15	1.03	.5	1.09	1.2	I	.23	.29	67.0	66.7	S21
24	83	200	.24	.15	1.07	1.4	1.08	1.3	J	.20	.30	58.0	63.8	S24
23	63	200	.72	.16	1.06	.9	1.07	.8	K	.19	.28	67.0	69.3	S23
6	138	200	-1.02	.16	.99	-.1	1.06	.7	L	.29	.29	74.0	70.7	S6
12	94	200	.00	.15	1.01	.3	1.01	.2	M	.29	.30	63.0	63.0	S12
26	93	200	.02	.15	1.01	.2	1.01	.1	N	.30	.30	64.5	63.0	S26
3	148	200	-1.28	.17	1.00	.0	1.00	.0	O	.28	.28	74.5	74.5	S3
5	156	200	-1.52	.18	.98	-.2	1.00	.0	n	.28	.27	81.0	78.1	S5
7	118	200	-.54	.15	1.00	.0	.99	-.2	m	.31	.31	65.5	65.2	S7
4	165	200	-1.83	.19	.98	-.1	.98	-.1	l	.27	.25	82.5	82.5	S4
11	53	200	.98	.17	.98	-.3	.94	-.5	k	.31	.26	75.0	73.7	S11
20	113	200	-.42	.15	.97	-.5	.96	-.7	j	.35	.31	66.0	64.3	S20
27	74	200	.45	.15	.97	-.5	.95	-.7	i	.34	.29	65.0	65.6	S27
13	133	200	-.89	.16	.94	-.9	.97	-.4	h	.37	.30	76.5	69.0	S13
19	114	200	-.45	.15	.96	-.9	.95	-.9	g	.37	.31	68.5	64.5	S19
25	104	200	-.22	.15	.95	-1.2	.95	-1.1	f	.38	.31	69.5	63.1	S25
2	94	200	.00	.15	.94	-1.5	.91	-1.8	e	.40	.30	63.0	63.0	S2
18	90	200	.09	.15	.92	-1.9	.90	-1.9	d	.42	.30	67.5	63.1	S18
28	81	200	.29	.15	.89	-2.3	.88	-2.1	c	.45	.30	72.5	64.2	S28
30	103	200	-.20	.15	.85	-3.6	.85	-3.3	b	.52	.31	72.0	63.1	S30
29	72	200	.50	.15	.83	-3.3	.78	-3.2	a	.54	.29	73.0	66.2	S29
MEAN	97.8	200.0	-.23	.21	1.00	-.1	1.01	.0				69.5	68.6	
S.D.	38.3	.0	1.48	.30	.07	1.5	.10	1.5				7.6	6.4	

Based on the results of the analysis of instrument trials to solve Mathematics story questions from 200 respondents with 30 questions. The obtained information for each evaluation item shows the level of suitability of the item to the measurement model used. Some items, such as Numbers 10, 15, and 23, show an excellent fit to the model, whereas others, such as Numbers 6 and 14, tend to be poor fit. Despite this, most items are still acceptable with quite good fit scores, although some have infit and outfit scores that are slightly above average. Further analysis may be needed to determine whether inappropriate items require revision or adjustment to improve their quality in the context of the measurement model used.

Furthermore, the second testing stage used much larger respondent data. In the second stage, the following results were obtained:

Table 2: Data on the distribution of misfit or unfit questions using the Rasch model for the second test

ENTRY NUMBER	TOTAL SCORE	COUNT	MEASURE	MODEL		INFIT		OUTFIT		PT-MEASURE		EXACT MATCH		ITEM	G
				S.E.	MNSQ	ZSTD	MNSQ	ZSTD	CORR.	EXP.	OBS%	EXP%			
12	94	300	1.66	.13	1.30	4.8	1.38	4.2	A	.00	.35	60.7	72.4	SB12	0
17	54	300	2.49	.16	1.17	1.7	1.35	2.3	B	.10	.31	80.7	82.8	SB17	0
18	120	300	1.23	.13	1.14	3.0	1.26	4.0	C	.17	.35	60.7	66.9	SB18	0
24	128	300	1.10	.12	1.18	4.1	1.24	3.9	D	.14	.35	60.0	65.5	SB24	0
23	99	300	1.57	.13	1.14	2.4	1.21	2.6	E	.18	.35	65.0	71.3	SB23	0
21	142	300	.88	.12	1.16	3.9	1.20	3.4	F	.17	.35	54.3	64.0	SB21	0
16	156	299	.67	.12	1.04	1.0	1.16	2.8	G	.28	.35	66.2	64.0	SB16	0
25	129	300	1.08	.12	1.10	2.4	1.10	1.8	H	.24	.35	55.0	65.4	SB25	0
3	299	300	-5.25	1.00	1.01	.3	1.09	.4	I	.02	.04	99.7	99.7	SB3	0
19	189	300	.16	.13	1.02	.5	1.00	.0	J	.31	.33	66.7	67.5	SB19	0
26	190	300	.14	.13	1.00	.1	.96	-.5	K	.34	.33	69.0	67.7	SB26	0
10	134	300	1.01	.12	.95	-1.2	1.00	.0	L	.39	.35	70.0	64.8	SB10	0
20	176	300	.36	.12	.99	-.2	.95	-.8	M	.36	.34	65.3	65.2	SB20	0
14	134	300	1.01	.12	.98	-.4	.99	-.2	N	.37	.35	64.0	64.8	SB14	0
4	292	300	-3.13	.36	.92	-.1	.97	.1	O	.24	.12	97.3	97.3	SB4	0
13	193	300	.09	.13	.97	-.7	.91	-1.2	n	.38	.33	70.7	68.3	SB13	0
7	258	300	-1.26	.17	.96	-.3	.93	-.3	m	.29	.25	85.7	86.1	SB7	0
8	270	300	-1.67	.20	.95	-.3	.82	-.8	l	.30	.22	90.0	90.0	SB8	0
30	210	300	-.20	.13	.94	-1.0	.92	-.9	k	.38	.32	72.7	72.3	SB30	0
9	156	300	.67	.12	.94	-1.6	.93	-1.2	j	.41	.35	71.0	63.9	SB9	0
5	288	300	-2.70	.30	.91	-.3	.51	-1.5	i	.30	.15	96.0	96.0	SB5	0
29	177	300	.35	.13	.91	-2.4	.85	-2.6	h	.46	.34	67.0	65.3	SB29	0
2	287	300	-2.61	.29	.90	-.3	.47	-1.7	g	.32	.15	95.7	95.7	SB2	0
22	122	300	1.19	.13	.90	-2.3	.85	-2.6	f	.47	.35	70.0	66.5	SB22	0
15	112	300	1.35	.13	.89	-2.3	.89	-1.7	e	.47	.35	76.0	68.4	SB15	0
11	139	300	.93	.12	.88	-3.1	.86	-2.7	d	.49	.35	73.7	64.2	SB11	0
6	283	300	-2.32	.25	.88	-.5	.55	-1.6	c	.35	.17	94.3	94.3	SB6	0
28	153	300	.72	.12	.87	-3.5	.83	-3.4	b	.50	.35	70.7	63.8	SB28	0
27	170	300	.46	.12	.84	-4.3	.79	-3.7	a	.53	.34	76.0	64.7	SB27	0
MEAN	177.7	300.0	.00	.19	1.00	.0	.96	-.1				73.9	73.8		
S.D.	67.4	.3	1.72	.17	.11	2.2	.22	2.2				12.9	12.3		

Based on the analysis of instrument trials for solving Mathematics story questions from 300 respondents with 30 questions. The obtained information for each evaluation item shows the level of suitability of the item to the measurement model used. In this table, several items, such as Numbers 12, 17, and 18, show poor fit with the measurement model as measured by the

value INFIT and quite a high OUTFIT. Despite this, most items were still well accepted, with some showing good fit values to the model. However, items Numbers 3 and 4 stand out as items with low goodness-of-fit values, which may require special attention to be corrected in the context of the measurement model. Further analysis can be performed to determine the cause of the nonconformity and appropriate corrective steps.

DISCUSSION

The analysis results show significant differences between the first trial and instrument development using the ADDIE method. The increase in item reliability scores from 0.96 to 0.98 indicates an increase in consistency in measuring students' abilities in solving mathematics story problems. Although person reliability increased from 0.58 to 0.67, this value still needs to be improved to ensure greater consistency in student performance evaluation. In addition, the Cronbach's alpha value remains stable at 0.918, indicating good internal consistency of the instrument.

Meanwhile, the increase in the separation score from 5.03 to 6.74 shows an increase in accuracy in measuring variations in student abilities. This indicates that the instrument developed can differentiate between students with different abilities more accurately.

Although the Outfit Mean Square Statistics (Outfit MNSQ) value tends to be stable at around 1.01 in both the person and item columns, a slight decrease from 1.01 to 0.96 in instrument development indicates an increase in the suitability between student responses and the Rasch measurement model. This indicates that the instrument developed can measure students' abilities better than the previous version.

In addition, the Outfit Z Standard (Outfit ZSTD) value, which is close to 0 in the person and item tables, indicates that student responses are consistent with the Rasch measurement model. However, it should be noted that an Outfit ZSTD value close to 0 does not guarantee that the instrument fully complies with the Rasch model, so further evaluation must be carried out to ensure its overall validity and reliability.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis results and comparison between the first trial and the development of the instrument using the ADDIE method, there is a significant increase in the quality of the instrument for the ability to solve mathematics story problems. The development of instruments using the ADDIE method and the application of the Rasch Model increased item reliability, personal reliability, and the instrument's ability to differentiate between students with different abilities. A stable Cronbach's alpha value indicates good internal consistency of the instrument. In contrast, an increase in the separation value indicates an increase in the accuracy of measuring variations in student abilities. Although some improvement is still needed in personal reliability, the instrument developed can measure student abilities better and more consistently than the previous version. These results indicate that developing an instrument for solving mathematics story problems using the ADDIE method and the Rasch Model is a

practical approach to improving the quality of evaluation in this field. The next step is to carry out further validation to ensure the suitability of the instrument shows an item score (item reliability) of 0.98, person reliability of 0.67, and a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.918, a separation value of 6.74 while an Outfit Mean Square Statistics (Outfit MNSQ) value) of 0.96 in the person and item columns. The Outfit Z Standard (Outfit ZSTD) value is 0.01 in the person table and -0.01 for the item table.

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